

LANGUAGE GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

In the article the theoretical underpinnings of efficiency of using language games in teaching English are shown. The complex of theoretical methods was drawn in the research: comparative analysis of methodical sources with the purpose of determination the state of developed research problem; analysis of didactical sources as for the integration language games to the process of teaching English; systematization of different researchers' views as for classification the language games.

The basic results of the article are determination the definition of "game", the advantages of using games, the study of didactic potential of language games in English lessons, description of the main forms, types, functions of language games, their classification.

It is shown the game is one of the fundamental learning activities. The games should be regarded as supplementary activities. When choosing a game, a teacher should be careful to find an appropriate one for the class in terms of language and type of participation. Once the game has begun, the teacher should not interrupt to correct mistakes in language use. The teacher should not compel an individual to participate. Games are serious devices by which we can create an interesting activity.

Games have following characteristics: they are based on a learning objective, give the player control over his own destiny, include doable challenges, they are fun and interesting, thus motivating, based on reality in order to intrinsically motivate the players to continue to play the game, they require interaction, must include everyone.

Some game forms are mentioned: information gap, guessing games, search games, matching games, matching-up games, exchanging games, collecting games, arranging games.

To use games effectively in the classroom a teacher should adhere to the following rules: the game must have a clear learning objective and purpose; the teacher should assign students to teams; be sure to explain all necessary procedures and rules clearly and slowly; be consistent; be prepared; maintain a non-threatening environment; it may be useful to have students create games.

The conclusion is to determine the rules for successful usage of games in the English classes as the game is one of the most effective forms of educational process organization and in the process of foreign language teaching at all levels is has the great pedagogical value.

Keywords: language game, usage, efficiency, learning, English, teacher, learner.

Костікова І. І. Дидактичні ігри у викладанні англійської мови. У статті виявлено теоретичне підґрунтя ефективності використання дидактичних ігор під час навчання англійської мови. У роботі використовувався комплекс методів теоретичного дослідження: порівняльний аналіз методичних джерел з метою визначення стану розробленості проблеми дослідження; аналіз навчально-методичної літератури щодо інтеграції у процес навчання англійської мови дидактичних ігор; систематизація поглядів різних дослідників на проблему класифікації дидактичних ігор. Основні результати роботи полягають у визначенні терміну «дидактична гра», з'ясуванні переваг використання ігор, дослідженні дидактичного потенціалу мовних ігор під час навчання англійської мови, описі основних форм, видів, функцій мовних ігор з англійської мови, їх класифікації.

Результатом проведеного дослідження є визначення правил ефективного використання ігор з англійської мови як однієї з найбільш ефективних форм організації навчального процесу, що у навчанні англійської мови на всіх рівнях має велику педагогічну цінність.

Ключові слова: дидактична гра, використання, ефективність, навчання, англійська мова, вчитель, учень.

Костікова И. И. Дидактические игры в преподавании английского языка. В статье выявлены теоретические основы эффективности использования дидактических игр в обучении английскому языку. В работе использовался комплекс методов теоретического исследования: сравнительный анализ методических источников с целью определения состояния разработанности проблемы исследования; анализ учебно-методической литературы по интеграции дидактических игр в процесс обучения английскому языку; систематизация взглядов разных исследователей на проблему классификации дидактических игр. Основные результаты работы заключаются в определении термина «дидактическая игра», выяснении преимуществ использования игр, исследовании дидактического потенциала языковых игр на уроках английского языка, описании основных форм, видов, функций языковых игр по английскому языку, их классификации.

Результатом исследования определены правила успешного использования игр на уроке английского языка как одной из наиболее эффективных форм организации учебного процесса, которая в обучении иностранному языку на всех уровнях имеет большую педагогическую ценность.

Ключевые слова: дидактическая игра, применение, эффективность, обучение, английский язык, учитель, ученик.

Statement of the problem. As we know nowadays Ukraine expands more and more relations with foreign countries, hence the interest in studying a foreign language is growing steadily. In the methodology of foreign language teaching there are various ways of optimization the educational activity, including the game. Games are covered in the methodological literature due to the fact that they attract foreign language teachers' interest because of the possibility using them as a mean of emotional release, motivation in educational activity, training, way to test students' knowledge and skills.

The work is dedicated to the problem of using language games at English lessons within the framework of communicative classroom. Taking part in various games impacts the development of attention, memory, thinking, imagination, all cognitive processes. For example, the pedagogical and didactic value of a game is that it allows participants to discover themselves, learn to act according to the circumstances; learn norms of behavior; leads to the development of certain language skills, ability to communicate, memorize the material.

However, it is important to state that the effectiveness of games as the educational way depends on their compliance with certain requirements, such as the presence of an imaginary situation, in which students will take part; children's awareness of the outcome of the game, its rules. The game is not just collective fun. This is the main way to achieve all of the tasks in education, therefore, teachers should know exactly what skills needed to improve. The game is a teaching tool that activates the mental children's activity, allows to make educational process more attractive and interesting, makes them worry in order to create a powerful stimulus in language acquisition.

It is important and appropriate to use various types of games, what games are effective and. Using games during the lesson is very important. Children like indoor and outdoor games, puzzles, crosswords, competitions. Conducting this activity, teacher is obliged to create a friendly atmosphere during a lesson, to accept children's

ideas concerning the rules of the game itself, remember that all participants are in equal conditions, maintain children's interest to the material.

Learning foreign language is the organization of children's education through games, which is caused by a number of factors. Firstly, intensification of educational process puts forward the objective of finding means of maintaining children's interest to the material and enhance them. One of the most effective means of solving this problem is the didactic games. Moreover, one of the major problems in teaching a foreign language is learning the spoken language, which in its turn creates the conditions for realizing communicative functions. The language allows to approach the learning process to the real training conditions which increase motivation for learning a foreign language. Children's involvement in oral communication can be successfully implemented in the context of playing activities.

The analysis of school textbooks shows that they don't provide a unified theoretical and didactic foundation for using language games. In case there are some language games in a book, it doesn't contain many of them or have a sufficient amount of communicative activities for developing vocabulary and grammar skills in speech activity.

It is known in the game especially full and sometimes unexpectedly reveals the ability of a person, especially a child. In school the special place occupied by such forms of work that provide an active part in the lesson, each pupil, increase the authority of knowledge and individual responsibility for the results of the pupil's work. The present method and practice of teaching children in elementary school focuses on the optimal combination of different forms, methods and teaching aids. This allows us to more effectively address training and educational objectives of the educational program. But learning tasks that performed in class, often determine the monotony of intellectual activity of student's by implementing a training goal – securing knowledge and skills development. This adversely affects the development of students and process of learning in the future. The priorities of secondary education significantly changed in recent years. Today, it's main goal – the

development of creative student's personality. When using games in the classroom, it is beneficial for teachers to have a complete understanding of the definitions of games, which usually are defined as a form of play concerning rules, competition, and an element of fun [15].

Review of Literature. Many scientists have paid attention to the study of the game: Richard-Amato [12], Ersoz [5], Carrier [4], Schultz [14], Hadfield [7], Lee [10]. They say that any game is one of the most important means of intellectual and moral education of children. Lessons using games and game situations are an effective means of upbringing and education, like the rest of the traditional constructions of the lesson the introduction of the game story attracted the attention of the entire class. *The urgency of this problem is* caused by the need of showing different approaches to using games.

The aim of the article is to study theoretical underpinnings of using language games in the classroom. **The objectives** of the article consist of showing the advantages of using games, analyzing the didactic potential of language games in English lessons, giving the definition of "game", description of its main forms, types, different classifications of the games, main demands to the games, the rules for successful usage of games in the English classes.

Presentation of the basic material. Games are fun activities that promote interaction, thinking, learning, and problem solving strategies. Often, games have an aspect that permits the players to produce information in a short time period. Some games require the players to engage in a physical activity and/or complete a mental challenge. It is known a 'GAME' is one of the fundamental useful learning activities in studying foreign languages. Games in language learning are effective and have great pedagogical value at all levels.

They also defined it as an organized activity that usually has the following properties: a particular task or objective, a set of rules, competition between players, and communication between players by spoken or written language [13, p.153] or as

an “activity with rules, a goal, and an element of fun” [7]. Language games are not activities mainly aimed to break the ice between students or to kill time.

Language learning is a hard task which can sometimes be frustrating. Constant effort is required to understand, produce and manipulate the target Language. Well-chosen games are invaluable as they give students a break and at the same time allow students to practice language skills. Games are highly motivating since they are amusing and at the same time challenging. Furthermore, they employ meaningful and useful language in real contexts. They also encourage and increase cooperation.

There are many advantages of using games in the classroom: 1) Games are a welcome break from the usual routine of the language class. 2) They are motivating and challenging. 3) Learning a language requires a great deal of effort, games help students to make and sustain the effort of learning. 4) Games provide language practice in the various skill-speaking, writing, listening and reading. 5) They encourage students to interact and communicate. 6) They create a meaningful context for language use.

Games have following characteristics: 1. They are based on a learning objective. 2. They give the player control over his own destiny. 3. They include doable challenges. 4. They are fun and interesting, thus motivating. 5. They are based on reality in order to intrinsically motivate the players to continue to play the game. 6. They require interaction. 7. Games must include everyone.

According to different writers there are different classifications of games. Lee [10, p.65] classifies games into ten kinds: structure games, vocabulary games, spelling games, pronunciation games, number games, listen-and-do games, read-and-do games, games and writing, miming and role-play, and discussion game. However, McCallum [11, p.74] categorizes games for language learning into seven kinds: vocabulary games, number games, structure games, spelling games, conversation games, writing games, and role-play and dramatics. From these two writers' division, we have five main kinds of games: vocabulary games, structure games, writing games, reading games, and games for developing speaking and listening skills. Each

kind of game focuses on a language component or a skill, so when choosing games, one of the factors that teachers have to consider is the aim of the lesson. As mentioned above, the language games chosen in this study must serve the purpose of helping the learners recall vocabulary; therefore, vocabulary games were chosen in this study.

According to Bradley [2], games have some characteristics that are advantageous to language learners as follows: First, games engage all students in the learning process. Second, games provide an opportunity for collaboration and/or cooperation. Third, games provide an enjoyable learning experience.

Hadfield [7, 8] said that games can take one of the following forms: A) Information gap. B) Guessing games. C) Search games. D) Matching games. E) Matching-up games. F) Exchanging games. G) Collecting games. H) Arranging games.

The second taxonomy that Hadfield [8, p.102 -104] uses to classify language games has many more categories. As with the classification of games as linguistic games or communicative games, some games will contain elements of more than one type: A) Sorting, ordering, or arranging games. B) Information gap games. C) Guessing games. D) Search games. E) Matching games. F) Labeling games. G) Exchanging games. H) Board games. I) Role-play games.

Nonetheless, Greenall [6, p.11] classifies games in a different way: A) Do-it-yourself simulation. B) Role-play. C) Describing. D) Matching pairs. E) Jigsaw. F) Logical sequences. G) Board games. H) Discussion. Activities can be used as a springboard for discussion or questionnaires.

These games can be played in pairs, groups, or with the whole class. They can be card games, board games, puzzles, and role-play according to the size of the class or the excitement of the games. Games are diverse and techniques used to carry them are various. They can be used at any stages of a class [9, p.101]. This study only focused on labelling games in which participants matched labels with pictures. In our

study we also single out three aspects of relevance of using educational games. The social aspect. The scientific aspect. The practical aspect.

To use games effectively in the classroom the teacher should adhere to the following rules.

The game must have a clear learning objective and purpose. It should be clear what the students are learning and practicing in the activities and procedures of the game. For example, for vocabulary identification the students can draw or act out the word. These games have a clear purpose and their format can be repeated in different sections or units.

The teacher should assign students to teams. The grouping may depend on many things but it should ultimately depend on the task the students will be completing. Having fair teams depends on knowing the students' abilities and personalities fairly well. Obviously, the latter option does not usually promote much discourse about the language or learning in general. Other students will try to pair up with the know-it-all and be carried through the game.

Be sure to explain all necessary procedures and rules clearly and slowly. Make sure everyone is listening and understands. If necessary, ask the students to restate

them. With games that have been played before, ask the students to state the rules and procedures prior to beginning game play.

Be consistent. If necessary, use a timer to make sure that everyone has the same amount of time to answer. Do not start another round if all the teams will not have a chance to go before class ends. Decide if only the first answer will be accepted because sometimes students say things incorrectly, realize it after they say it and then fix it.

Be prepared. Make sure that there are enough materials, time, questions, etc. As an educator the unexpected always happens: an assembly, absent students, extra or not enough time. It is the facilitator's job to make educated and well-thought out decisions on the spot. Knowing how the game works helps making those decisions.

Maintain a non-threatening environment. All standard classroom rules and procedures should be observed when playing games. For example, unacceptable behaviour should include name calling and belittling. Before we play our very first game we discuss how to treat and talk to others. Additionally, by saying those things certain students may become less likely to participate and thus their learning is curtailed and they are entitled to more. Furthermore, it is just generally hurtful and mean.

It may be useful to have students create games. It can be only recommend after the students have had exposure to educational games in the classroom setting so that they are familiar with game operation and how the teacher chooses to manage them. It is important to set boundaries or requirements for the games so that the students can narrow the focus of their creativity. Games allow the students to show a little of their true personalities, build relationships with others, and practice various skills. They also allow the facilitator to see who knows the information and who is or is not afraid to share it. Also it becomes more apparent what students need more instruction or what concepts can or cannot be performed adequately.

Conclusions. To summarize it all, we can say that, basically, game is one of the fundamental learning activities and not only in studying foreign languages.

Games in language learning at all levels have great pedagogical value. It was well documented in different scientific works and articles. Apart from their motivational value as an enjoyable form of activity, they provide a context in which the language is embedded. This context is 'authentic' in the sense that the game creates its own world: for the duration of the game, it replaces external reality. Games also create the circumstances for meaningful repetition. Furthermore, the same game can be played many times yet never produce identical outcomes. Needless to say, games also ensure that the players interact with each other, and this interaction is usually played out in language.

We can conclude that games should be regarded as supplementary activities. The whole syllabus should not be based on games only – even for young learners. When choosing a game, the teacher should be careful to find an appropriate one for the class in terms of language and type of participation. Once the game has begun, the teacher should not interrupt to correct mistakes in language use. The teacher should not compel an individual to participate. Some learners may not want to participate due to personal reasons. Forcing students to participate usually does not have successful results. A game which looks wonderful on the paper may not work in the actual classroom setting. If it is tiring or boring, it should be stopped. Give clear instructions. Unless the learners know what he is expected to do and how to do it, the aim cannot be achieved, and the game cannot be played. Games are serious devices by which we can create an interesting activity.

Prospects. The perspectives of future papers may show how students can learn grammar, vocabulary items using games as well as a game can help both young and adults. It will be interesting to show students' motivation as well as games help engage all students, provide an opportunity for collaboration and cooperation, and provide an enjoyable learning experience.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Avedon, M.E. and Brian, B.S. (1971) Learning through Games. The Study of Games. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc: pp 315-321.

2. Bradley L., Lindstrm, B. and Rystedt, H. (2010) Rationalities of collaboration for language learning in a wiki, *ReCALL*, 22(2), 247-265.
3. Byrne, D. (1995). *Games. Teaching Oral English*. Harlow: Longman Group UK Limited: pp. 101-103.
4. Carrier, M. (1990). *Take 5: Games and Activities for the Language Learner*, UK: pp. 6-11.
5. Ersoz, A. (2000). Six games for the EFL/ESL classroom. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 6 (6). Retrieved on January 22, 2011, from <http://iteslj.org/Lessons/Ersoz-Games.html>
6. Greenall, S. (1990). *Language games and activities*. Britain: Hulton Educational Publications Ltd. p.11
7. Hadfield, J. (1990). *A Collection of Games and Activities for Low to Mid-Intermediate students of English. Intermediate Communication Games*. Hong Kong: Thomus and Nelson and Nelson and Sons Ltd.
8. Hadfield, J. (1999). *Beginners' communication games*. London: Longman. p.102 -104
9. Harmer, J. (1991). *The practice of English language teaching*. London: Longman. p.101
10. Lee, W.R. (2000). *Language teaching games and contests*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. p.65
11. McCallum, G.P. (1980). *101 Word Games*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. p.74
12. Richard-Amato, P. A. (1996). *Making it happen*. New York: Addison-Wesley Publishing Group. pp. 192-199.
13. Richards, J. C., Platte, J. & Platte, H. (1992). *Dictionary of language teaching and applied linguistics*. London: Longman. p.153.
14. Schultz, M. and Fisher. A. (1988). *Interacting in the Language Classroom. Games for All Reasons*. Massachusetts: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company.
15. Kostikova, I. and Al-karawi, M. (2016) Using language games at English lessons. *Young professionals are science future: Collection of students' scientific works*. Kharkiv: V.Karazin HhNU. Vol. 7. p. 9 – 17.